

Interview guide for Case Study #2:

Rituals of Extended Conventional Deterrence: NATO-Russia (post-Cold War)

1. What does deterrence mean to you in principle? What makes deterrence work militarily and politically, in your assessment?
2. How important is efficient signalling for deterrence to succeed in your assessment?
3. What should credible extended deterrence entail in the contemporary security environment in Europe in general and in NATO's north-eastern flank in particular?
4. Please describe the key junctures in the process of constructing NATO's Enhanced Forward Presence into the Alliance's eastern flank.
5. In your estimation, are there any historical analogies that have informed the specifics of NATO's allied posture in Poland and the Baltic states?
6. What does serving as the framework/participant nation of a NATO's eFP battlegroup in the eastern flank mean for your country?
7. What have been the main lessons drawn from your country's experience with the eFP to date?
8. How do you see the pros and cons for a permanent versus rotational presence of allied forces in the Alliance's eastern flank?
9. Where do you see the main distinction between the tripwire and forward defence postures in NATO's eastern flank?
10. What do you see as the most notable loopholes in NATO's strategy and posture to deter potential aggression from Russia to the Alliance, particularly in the eastern flank?
11. What do you take to be the long-term implications of the Russo-Ukrainian war for the Alliance's deterrence and defence strategy, including for the allied nuclear deterrence policy?
12. What do you see as the likely conflict scenarios between Russia and NATO in the medium-term? What kind of a power do you take Russia to be? In your assessment, how has NATO's perception of Russia changed since the end of the Cold War?